

Voices from the Classroom: Unraveling Teachers' Experiences in Integrating Gender and Development

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Abstract. This study explored and investigated the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights learned from the experiences of High school teachers in integrating Gender and Development (GAD) in instruction. Qualitative approach to research phenomenological from the ten high school teachers from Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. On the experiences of high school teachers in integrating Gender and Development in instruction, the following were observed: Lack of training, Deep-Rooted Gender Stereotypes, and Lack of Suitable Teaching Resources. While on the high school teachers coping mechanism on the challenges encountered in integrating GAD in instruction, the following were observed: Teacher Training and Professional Development, Life Skills and Empowerment Education, and Textbook and Learning Material Evaluation. Through their experiences and coping mechanisms, we generated new knowledge and ideas on the experiences encountered by high school teachers in integrating Gender and Development in instruction. Finally, the educational management insights learned from the experiences of high school teachers were the complexity of Gender Integration, the Importance of Teacher Training, and the Long-Term Perspective on GAD. These themes can be described as input in the successful crafting and conduct of training for teachers to capacitate them on the different strategies and techniques in integrating GAD in instruction. It may be published in a reputable research journal.

KEY WORDS

1. Gender and Development
2. Gender and Development
3. Teaching Resources

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1. Introduction

Teachers can use body language - a look, a position, a signal - to communicate simple, positive, and respectful messages to their students without saying a single word. Teachers can also help students become aware of what their body language is saying. The tone of voice is a powerful way to convey teachers' caring, understanding, and openness. "It is easy to forget when we are stressed or tired, but teachers can provide a positive learning environment when they are thoughtful in their tone of voice. "Voices from the classroom as the unraveling of teachers' ex-

periences in integration. Likewise, ensure that any educational materials used show genders in equal measure. Mix boys and girls to work on projects together. Explore gender concepts and roles from different communities. Help students identify instances of gender bias through awareness activities or historical events, laws, and cultural changes. Schools are environments where gender issues become evident. Numerous studies have highlighted various forms of discrimination experienced by both boys and girls, indicating that significant adjustments are still required to achieve equality and equal opportunities, particularly in terms of the strategies

employed. Addressing these issues presents a considerable challenge for teachers, as they must cater to the diverse needs of their students. Unfortunately, teachers may sometimes overlook the importance of considering the gender of their students (Hernandez, T. A., Cudiamat, M. A. 2018). The Gender and Development Program (GAD), as defined by the Magna Carta of Women (Republic Act No. 9710), embodies a development perspective and approach that is inclusive, empowering, fair, and sustainable. It aims to create an environment free from violence, respectful of human rights, and supportive of self-determination and the realization of human potential. The program's ultimate goal is to promote gender equality as a fundamental value integrated into all development decisions, recognizing that women play an active role as agents of development rather than merely being passive recipients. According to the Government Service insurance system, GAD emphasizes Gender Mainstreaming, which is a strategic approach that involves: Integrating women's and men's perspectives, concerns, and experiences into the entire process of designing, implementing, monitoring, and evaluating policies, programs, and projects across all aspects of society, including social, political, civil, and economic domains. This ensures that both women and men can equally benefit from these initiatives. It is evaluating the potential effects on women and men of any proposed action, including legislation, policies, or programs, in all sectors and at every level. This assessment is essential to address gender disparities and promote gender equality in all areas of society. Gender and Development (GAD) is an approach to development that acknowledges the unequal status and circumstances women and men face in society. It involves a participatory and empowering process that aims to be fair, sustainable, free from violence, and respectful of human rights. Additionally, GAD supports self-determination and the realization of human potential. Simultaneously, it addresses women's strategic interests and the needs of the economically disadvantaged through people-centered development and gender mainstreaming initiatives. The Department of Education (DepEd) introduced the Gender-Responsive Basic Education (GRBE) Policy to fulfill its Gender and Development mandate as outlined in the 1987 Philippine Constitution, aiming to eradicate all forms of discrimination against women and uphold the rights of children, among other objectives (DepEd Order No. 32, s. 2017). The Philippine government fully acknowledges and endorses the importance of GRBE. By implementing the GRBE policy, DepEd pledges to incorporate the principles of gender equality and non-discrimination in the provision of basic education. Gender responsiveness involves acknowledging the diverse requirements of girls and boys, as well as men and women, and taking appropriate measures to address these distinct needs while preventing gender bias or discrimination. By actively confronting gender inequality and bias, gender responsiveness works towards promoting gender equality. (Galamgam, M., Bautista, J., Eblacas, I., Rosario, E. (2021). Hernandez and Cudiamat (2018) emphasize the importance of incorporating a gender-responsive teaching approach in the classroom, as it plays a crucial role in promoting gender equality and positively impacting the academic performance of learners. UNGEI (United Nations Girls' Education Initiative) emphasizes the significance of examining educational policies through a gender lens, as they impact both girls and boys. Conducting a gender analysis of education policies allows for the identification of differences and disparities, leading to the formulation of suitable actions to address them (Johnson et al., 2016). Talon et al. (2020) discovered that implementing Gender-Responsive Basic Education (GRBE) in schools is crucial to ensure that all learners, particularly during work im-

mersion, are not subjected to discrimination in their future careers. The adoption of GRBE is seen as a means to benefit all students and create a fair and equitable learning environment. Gender-responsive education initiatives aimed at enhancing access to and successful completion of high-quality education for both girls and boys create multiple positive impacts. Studies have demonstrated that when girls have increased access to education, it leads to beneficial outcomes across generations, including improvements in health, nutrition, infant mortality, and income generation, among other advantages. Academic institutions, such as the Department of Education, hold a crucial responsibility in tackling gender disparity within the country's education system. They must provide institutional support to students of all genders, ensuring that gender equality is a fundamental aspect of their strategies and approaches. (Galamgam, M., Bautista, J., Eblacas, I., Rosario, E. (2021). Educators play a crucial role in fostering gender equity within schools, as studies have indicated that their gender-stereotyped beliefs and instructional methods significantly impact gender disparities in students (Gundersen et al., 2012; Heyder et al., 2020). Education holds a crucial role in molding a child's mindset, particularly during their early formative years. This period offers a prime opportunity to instill profound and meaningful ideas while promoting the breaking of stereotypes. By providing children with a gender-neutral education through various creative avenues like arts, drama, music, and both formal and informal curricula, we aim to encourage young minds to question, challenge, and counter prevailing societal norms they encounter at home, in media, or within

their communities. (Sen, S. 2022) Teachers play a significant role in modeling gender equality and preparing children for a changing world, where traditional beliefs about male and female roles no longer apply. The gender-neutral language used in classrooms and the diverse stories about women and men in non-stereotyped roles that students read can greatly influence their future interests, activities, and career choices. By creating a safe and inclusive learning environment that is free from violence and discrimination and providing gender-sensitive education, teachers contribute to positive change. Governments have a part to play in promoting gender equality in education by developing non-discriminatory curricula, facilitating teacher education, and ensuring adequate sanitation facilities in schools. Schools can also encourage teachers to follow professional norms regarding appropriate disciplinary practices and provide unbiased instruction. Moreover, acknowledging and accepting femininity and masculinity as unique gifts from a higher power allows for mutual enrichment and a deeper appreciation of each other's strengths.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study was to determine the experiences of public high school teachers in integrating gender and development, their coping mechanisms, and the insights learned from the experiences of the informants.

1.2. Research Questions—The research aimed to gather opinions and firsthand accounts of high school teachers working in public schools regarding the challenges associated with integrating Gender and Development. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What obstacles do high school teachers encounter in integrating gender and development?
- (2) How do high school teachers cope with the challenges of integrating gender and development?
- (3) What are the educational insights learned from the experiences of the informants?

To explore the outcomes of this study and to whom the findings are addressed, the following persons or agencies were the beneficiaries. Department of Education Officials. The DepEd officials ought to be more open, accepting, and understanding when it comes to Gender and Development and the challenges that follow, especially in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. It may also be feasible to develop particular policies that will assist teachers in integrating Gender and Development to the fullest extent possible and providing high-quality instruction. The teachers. This study's findings were helpful to teachers as they uncovered how the participants feel about the impediments posed by integrating Gender and Development in education and how they have overcome those obstacles. The learners. This research would provide the reader with a complete sense of how teachers manage and overcome difficulties in integrating Gender and Development. This study would also explore high school teachers' significant challenges and experiences when integrating Gender and Development. Future researchers. Future researchers should consider some other components of the high school teachers' experiences that were not covered in this study. To better compare the phenomenon being studied, additional areas pertaining to this study may be conducted in other grade levels and districts.

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following were the terms used to make the study more comprehensive. Gender and Development - an approach to development that acknowledges the unequal status and circumstances women and men face in society. It involves a participatory and empowering process that aims to be fair, sustainable, free from violence, and respectful of human rights. Additionally, GAD supports self-determination and the realization of human potential.

1.4. Review of Significant Literature—This chapter examines the key studies on gender integration, teacher training, and resource avail-

ability, providing insights into the challenges and strategies relevant to this study.

1.4.1. Gender and Development—The Magna Carta of Women (RA 9710) and the Department of Science and Technology (2021) underscore GAD's role in promoting gender parity and empowering women as agents of change. The Gender Roles framework highlights how identities are constructed within households, while the Social Relations Analysis exposes hierarchical dynamics affecting gender status in society. Gender Mainstreaming, backed by the Philippine Commission on Women (2020), aims for a society that equally values contributions from all genders.

1.4.2. High School Teachers' Experiences with GAD Integration—Education initiatives, such as EFA and MDGs, have improved access, yet gender parity in enrollment remains unachieved globally (Durrani Halai, 2020). Teachers face barriers due to limited training (UNESCO, 2015), insufficient resources, and inadequate technology access. This training gap restricts teachers' ability to deliver gender-focused instruction effectively (Sakko, 2022). Gender stereotypes deeply influence learning environments, as seen in social expectations and the parenting landscape (Babu, 2023), affecting students' confidence and behavior (Mittal, 2023).

1.4.3. Challenges with Resources—Lack of resources compromises students' education quality, especially in underprivileged areas, leading to lower academic performance and fewer learning opportunities (Maffea, 2020; Kapur, 2022). Schools in rural areas are particularly affected by inadequate teaching resources, posing obstacles to achieving educational objectives (Martinelli, 2018).

1.4.4. Strategies for GAD Success—Teacher Training and Professional Development: Equipping teachers with GAD-sensitive tools can foster inclusive environments and reduce biases (McKinley, 2022). This train-

ing enables educators to act as role models and implement gender-responsive education (Global Partnership for Education, 2020). Life Skills and Empowerment Education: Integrating critical life skills fosters students' abilities to challenge harmful gender norms, supporting gender equality and empowering diverse gender identities (European Institute for Gender Equality, 2023; Mani, 2014). Textbook and Material Evaluation: Ensuring educational materials reflect diverse gender identities promotes inclusivity, enhancing student engagement and critical thinking (Read, 2015; Calhoun, Sahay Wilson, 2021). Insights from Informants: The complexity of integrating gender in education reflects deeply rooted cultural norms (UNESCO, 2019) and patriarchal values (Enriquez, 2023). Teacher training equips educators to create inclusive learning environments that challenge stereotypes and foster gender equity (Ecole, 2023).

1.4.5. Long-Term Perspective on GAD—A sustained commitment is essential to embed gender equality into cultural, legal, and institutional frameworks. This approach aligns with global standards like CEDAW, the Beijing Declaration, and the SDGs, providing a roadmap for long-term progress (OECD, 2022; UN Women, 2019).

1.5. Theoretical Lens—The research was directed by the Gender Schema theory, which is a theory rooted in cognition and employs an information processing method to elucidate the process of gender development. This theory relies on a cognitive framework known as a schema, which serves as a cognitive structure facilitating the simplification and classification of novel information. Two categories of gender-related schemas exist, as outlined by Martin and Halverson in 1981. The initial schema is a broad 'superordinate' framework aiding children in classifying objects, traits, and attributes into fundamental male and female divisions. The subsequent schema is a more specific vari-

ant known as the 'own-sex' schema, utilized by children to recognize and comprehend comprehensive information aligning with their own gender. These two types of schemas enable children to assimilate details about events, items, attitudes, actions, and roles, subsequently classifying these elements based on their association with masculinity or femininity, or their likeness or dissimilarity to the child (Martin Halverson 1981). Essentially, Kohlberg claimed that between age two and seven, children learn to understand that their sex is unchangeable. After this time, he argued, children came to understand and take on gender roles as they observed them in society. Gender schema theory is a cognitively based theory that uses an information—processing approach to explain how gender development occurs. The basis of this model is the cognitive representation called a schema. A schema is an organizing structure that helps simplify and categorize new information. The nature of schemas as tools for interpreting and classifying information can sometimes lead to the formulation of inaccurate conclusions. This misinterpretation of information is also associated with gender-oriented cognitive processing. Gender schema theory highlights the child's role as an engaged interpreter of information, underlining that the gender-related frameworks steering cognition also impact children's actions. The primary advantage of gender schema theory lies in its capacity to illuminate the preservation and potency of gender-related convictions. (Martin, Dinella, 2001). Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. It shows three interconnected themes. The experiences of High School teachers in Integrating Gender and Development, a qualitative inquiry that allows researchers to focus on engaging in meaningful inquiry about their professional practice, would enhance this practice of the learning community. There was a genuine concern, as could be viewed with the first circle, a coping mechanism for the challenges encountered by high

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

school teachers in integrating gender and development, which interlinks to the second circle, and their interconnection was insight from their experiences.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitates the consequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter.

The three most common qualitative methods were participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when exploring sensitive topics. Focus groups effectively elicit data on a group's cultural norms and generate broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as inquiry that asks the question, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" "the goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand the experiences of the BE Coordinators as they try to compare its implementation then and now. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation greater in depth and

breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested that information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions of the Study—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research begins with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm), meaning pattern, model, or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an action of submitting to a view. This view was supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who defend a research paradigm as a "basic set of beliefs that guide action," dealing with first principles, "ultimates' or the researcher's worldview

or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by the study participants. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the participants discuss teachers' experiences in remote teaching and try to look into their strategies for addressing the challenges and providing educational insights. In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant's answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), state that the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself and the participants on the epistemological assumption. He suggests that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an 'insider'. Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). The researcher identified phenomenology using thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief." This study intended to gather information from the participants or teachers in Tugbok Dis-

trict in Integrating Gender and Development. It was assured that close interaction with the participants was established to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the experiences and strategies used in integrating Gender and Development. Axiology refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) argued that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggested that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with participants' interpretation. The researcher ensured the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric. It means reporting what reality was through the eyes of the research participants. This was important because it meant that the researcher would report objectively what was observed and heard from the participants. The research used personal voice and qualitative terms and limited definitions. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person in elucidation of the experiences of teachers as they integrate Gender and Development.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology was different from the method. The methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the challenges experienced by the High School teachers in integrating Gender and Development in Tugbok District were gathered through an In-Depth Interview (IDI), and their coping mechanisms were extracted from the participants. The researcher's drive to know the deeper meaning of the challenges experi-

enced by high school teachers in integrating Gender and Development (GAD) became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means of which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for “meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena”. Using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the challenges experienced by High School teachers in integrating GAD in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs, (2006), that experience was a source of knowledge and shapes one’s behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge. We can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology, which concerns the “what” and the “how” (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the challenges experienced and mechanisms used by the high school teachers were explored and insights drawn, which will form the basis for possible future research and policy analysis in relation to this research.

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design. According to Creswell, (2012), phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research focused on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a

description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes that were grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) also added that phenomenology, with its roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, attempts to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, the researcher uses bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects’ perspective. Creswell (2012) also claimed that interviews were primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews are also useful for following up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as further investigating their responses. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees said (McNamara, 1999). Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2016), the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews particularly help uncover the story behind a participant’s

experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. The researcher collected data from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via long interviews. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation, extracting significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied together to make a general description of the experience, a textural description of what was experienced, and a structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had actually experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult to do. The researcher also needed to decide how and when his or her personal observations should be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to explore and assess the teacher experience and feelings towards the school environment and the perspectives of the seasoned teachers, the researcher intends to employ the phenomenology type of qualitative method re-

search.

2.4. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations are significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participant in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations can be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needs to adhere to the aims of the research, imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and prevention of error. Social Value. The research was essential to society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experience of teachers. This study was specifically conducted among the elementary teachers. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushes the researcher's interest is the challenges the teachers face in using interactive media instruction in the classroom as a way to ameliorate teaching competence. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary in nature and was based on the understanding of adequate information. The participant recruitment and selection were lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgement, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The informed consent letter aims to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary par-

participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the letter of consent to the researcher before participating in the research. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The participants of this study could answer the research instrument because they are all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as the researcher, he or she can easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions concerning the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, if respondents experienced potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelling to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher ensured the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered at their convenience. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their natural sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were considered so there would be no conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided. Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to be fully honest in answering the survey questions and that any type of communication related to the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the study's results. Transparency. The respondents accessed the results of the study, and the heads of the participating schools because the information was available. The information will be placed on CD or other storage devices, which can be requested from the researcher. In addition, by learning on the results of the study, classroom teachers will be aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process. They can be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview. This allowed the participants to amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to use pseudonyms and change names and non-significant dates in the interest of protecting the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that he or she was qualified to conduct the study. The researcher should have completed the academic requirements and passed the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the master's degree. The researcher should also be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strived to ensure

that the study could be completed successfully in the specified time and that he or she was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by giving suggestions and recommendations for improving it. Also, the researcher ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed within the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher respected the respondents' local traditions, culture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study did not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in the recruitment of the participants or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher necessarily expressed great pleasure in the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else had said his or her way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present when working on the manuscript and no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results was included, or that conclusions were purposefully put forward that were not accurate.

2.5. *Research Participants*—The participants of this study were Ten (10) teachers from Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) must be in the service for at least 5 years; (2) high school teacher; and (3) experienced integrating Gender and Development. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall,

1996).

2.6. *Roles of the Researcher*—The researcher was responsible for uncovering, transferring, and exploiting knowledge to benefit educational institutions. To do so, the researcher takes up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher conducts interviews with the participants and guides them in the process. The researcher interprets ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies and not on the researcher's own knowledge, thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative methods. The researcher implements the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assesses himself and seeks help from the research adviser and other research professionals. These help him exhibit competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews properly according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. The researcher ensures different ways of making a record of what is said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio or video recording. The recordings are transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. Records done by the researcher were correctly secured as they contained sensitive information and were relevant to the research. However, the data were being collected, and the researcher's primary responsibility was safeguarding participants and their data. Mechanisms for safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins. Analyst of data. The researcher sought the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading

between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher ensured that the findings were true to the participants and that their voices were heard. The researcher organizes and presents data. The researcher presents the problem and the related literature and studies that support it. The study's findings are presented, too, by the research question, stating the results for each one using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, the researcher gives future directions and implications of the study for improving educational policy and practices.

2.7. Data Collection—The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher is willing to send a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters 1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument explaining the study's objectives and identifying the participants. The researcher would wait for the response of the SDS before conducting the study. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher asked permission from the participants and their parents/guardians. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. The researcher transcribed the interviewees' responses precisely by

recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it to English. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. After the transcription, the data will then be categorized and coded. Then, themes was extracted and individual data within the participants was compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants; additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

2.8. Data Analysis—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis. The researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with their data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involving generating pithy labels for essential features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a data reduction method but also an analytic process, so codes capture a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ends this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The

researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each theme and the relationship between the themes. Thematic Content Analysis was employed by the researcher for these. Thematic Content Analysis was a descriptive presentation of qualitative data in which a detailed analysis of each theme was made by identifying the ‘essence’ of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy and informative name for each theme (Andersen, 2013). In addition, to enhance validity and to create a more in-depth picture of the phenomenon, Environmental Triangulation was also employed by the researcher. It was a technique to analyze the results of the same study using different methods of data collection. The key was identifying which environmental factors, if any, might influence the information that is received during the study. These environmental factors are changed to see if the findings are the same across the settings (David, 2015). This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors such as time, day, and season in which the study occurred. The idea was to determine which of these factors influenced the information received, and these factors were then changed to see if the findings were the same. Validity can be established if the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement, as mentioned, was the use of environmental triangulation best suited to the environment of the research being conducted. Writing-up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature.

2.9. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In qualitative study, trustworthiness was

very important because the result and finding of the research study would depend on the process of how it was being conducted by the researcher. The trustworthiness of a research study is important to evaluate its worth. Due to the nature of qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details are required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher’s study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. Credibility was how confident the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the research study’s findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do was essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues that ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2000) state that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue is “how we ensure rigor in the research process and how we communicate to others that we have done so.” Transferability is how the qualitative researcher demonstrates that the research study’s findings are applicable to other contexts. In this case, “other contexts” can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher have already studied the effects of using graphic organizer as strategy in teaching reading comprehension. The use of graphic organizer as a strategy in teaching reading comprehension is effective in the domains analysis and creating. With this, the researcher is interested to know the students’ perspective of using this strategy. Gasson (2004) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader was able to provide generalization of the study based on his own context and can able to address that core issue of “how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory.” Confirmability was the degree of neutrality in the research study’s findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on participants’ responses and not any potential bias or personal motivations of the researcher. This involves making sure that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of what the re-

search participants said to fit a certain narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Gasson (2004) states that confirmability was based on the acknowledgement that research is never objective. Dependability was the extent that the study could be repeated by other researchers and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher used inquiry audit in order to establish dependability which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis in order to ensure that the findings are consistent and could be repeated. In this component, the use of database was very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected was kept correctly for future use as references. Gasson (2004) stated that dependability deals with the core issue that "how a study is conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques."

2.10. Analytical Framework—The framework analysis of this research was flexible to allow the researcher to either collect all the data and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. In the analysis stage, the gathered data was sifted, charted, and sorted by key issues and themes. This involves a five-step process: (1) familiarization, (2) identifying a thematic framework, (3) indexing, (4) charting, and (5) mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization refers to the process during which the researcher becomes familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected (i.e., interview or focus group tran-

scripts, observation, or field notes) and gains an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). In other words, the researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher will become aware of key ideas and recurrent themes and make a note of them. Due to the sheer volume of data that can be collected in qualitative research, the researcher may not be able to review all the material. Thus, a selection of the data set would be utilized. The selection would depend on several aspects of the data collection process. For example, the mix of methods used (e.g. interviews, documents, observations), The second stage of identifying a thematic framework occurs after familiarization when the researcher recognizes emerging themes or issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues may have arisen from a priori themes; however, at this stage, the researcher must allow the data to dictate the themes and issues. To achieve this end the researcher uses the notes taken during the familiarization stage. The key issues, concepts and themes that have been expressed by the participants now form the basis of a thematic framework that can be used to filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Indexing means identifying portions or sections of the data that correspond to a particular theme. This process is applied to all the textual data that has been gathered (e.g., transcripts of interviews). For the sake of convenience, Ritchie and Spencer recommend that a numerical system be used for the indexing references and annotated in the margin beside the text (1994). Qualitative data analysis tools are ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping, and interpretation, involves the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis should be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, thus guiding the researcher in their interpretation of the data set. At this point, the researcher was cognizant of the objectives

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

of qualitative analysis: “defining concepts, mapping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies” (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994, p. 186). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations reflect the participant. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations made by the researcher echo the participants’ true attitudes, beliefs, and values.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses the outcomes of the interview data analysis, highlighting the identified themes and their accompanying in-depth discussions aligned with the study’s objectives. The presentation primarily focuses on the background and descriptions of participants, all assigned pseudonyms to safeguard their privacy.

3.1. *Experiences of High School Teachers in Integrating Gender and Development*—Education and the promotion of gender equality remain central themes within the development agenda, particularly in the aftermath of the international consensus established through the Education for All (EFA) and Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) initiatives. Despite the criticisms leveled against EFA and MDGs, their instigated efforts have yielded notable progress in the expansion of educational access. However, at a global scale, the objective of achieving gender parity in enrollment remains unrealized in primary education (in over 33 percent of countries), lower secondary education (in

54percent of countries), and upper secondary education (in 77percent of countries) (Durrani, N., Halai, A. (2020). The aim of this study is to collect insights and firsthand narratives from grade two teachers employed in public schools, specifically focusing on their experiences in integrating gender and development. The participants’ responses were organized into themes encompassing essential concepts and diverse ideas for development. The transcripts from this focus group discussion, rooted in the obtained interview data, were systematically classified according to the participants’ encounters and the challenges they faced in incorporating gender and development principles within the

classroom.

3.1.1. Lack of Training—Education is the cornerstone of societal advancement, shaping the destinies of individuals and communities. Teachers are central to the efficacy of education and play a crucial role in imparting knowledge, skills, and values to the succeeding generation. However, a noteworthy challenge that undermines the quality of education is the issue of inadequate training for teachers. UNESCO has identified factors contributing to the scarcity of research training opportunities. One primary factor is the insufficient duration for educators to be away from their educational institutions for extended professional development sessions. Face-to-face, multi-day programs are particularly beneficial for Comprehensive Sexual Education (CSE) teachers, as they afford ample time for assimilating and practicing skills. These training sessions are often scheduled during school breaks, necessitating teachers to forego essential periods of relaxation and family time (UNESCO, 2015). The responses align with what has been mentioned in the Encyclopedia on Early Childhood Development from 2013. It emphasizes how schools play a crucial role in shaping kids' views on gender, influenced by both teachers and peers. The book points out that, unfortunately, many teachers lack proper training in recognizing and addressing gender stereotypes, whether it's their own or others'. This often leads to unintentional reinforcement of gender differences instead of challenging them. Consequently, schools end up perpetuating traditional gender biases and disparities. However, educators committed to gender equality take proactive steps, like encouraging interactions between genders, introducing non-stereotypical role models, and discussing ways to counter gender stereotypes and harassment. This kind of approach can significantly enhance students' developmental outcomes.

3.1.2. Deep-Rooted Gender Stereotypes—Gender stereotypes involve deeply ingrained

ideas and expectations about the roles and characteristics attributed to men and women in our society. These preconceived notions have the potential to significantly impact an individual's development and contribute to imbalances within the broader societal framework. Additionally, within the realm of parenting, gender stereotypes can have lasting effects on a child's social and emotional growth (Babu, 2023). In numerous cultures, prevailing societal norms rigidly define distinctions between genders and prescribe specific roles for each. These deeply ingrained convictions reflect the broader expectation that individuals should adhere to the expected behaviors and decisions associated with their assigned gender. Instances of such gender-stereotyped beliefs are widespread, evident in actions like parents choosing strongly gendered toys for their children or subtly guiding them toward certain educational and career paths deemed appropriate for their gender. Social resistance or disapproval may also arise when women display traits such as assertiveness or ambition. When these beliefs become firmly embedded in a society, influencing individual choices and outcomes, they significantly contribute to gender-based achievement gaps and the underrepresentation of women in high-level executive roles and leadership positions (Alan, Ertac, Mumco, 2017). The natural development of gender is something every child goes through. To encourage positive gender development in young kids, an important strategy educators can use is understanding the concept of gender identity and where it comes from. Gender identity is how individuals internally see themselves, shaped by a mix of their biological characteristics, developmental influences, and the environment around them (How gender disparities affect classroom learning, 2021).

3.1.3. Lack of Suitable Teaching Resources—The limited supply of teaching resources has diverse consequences for students, hindering them from experiencing the best pos-

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes on the Experiences of High School Teachers in Integrating Gender and Development

sible education. It means they only partially grasp topics and lessons, missing out on the thorough understanding they should rightfully receive. According to The Commonwealth Institute (2017), students in schools situated in economically disadvantaged areas grapple with challenges like lower scores on standardized tests, increased instances of chronic absenteeism, a higher chance of repeating a grade, and a diminished likelihood of graduating on time. This emphasizes the considerable negative impact that the lack of resources has on students facing such circumstances (Maffea, J.,

2020). As per (Kapur, R., 2022), educators and supervisors across different educational levels are primarily dedicated to imparting knowledge on various academic subjects and lesson content. Their challenge stems from the inadequacy of teaching methods and resources, hindering their effectiveness in fulfilling their roles. Conversely, students are chiefly focused on thoroughly mastering academic subjects and lesson plans. They adopt a systematic approach to understanding these subjects and plans, aspiring to meet the expectations of educators and supervisors and earn their degrees.

Consequently, the lack of proper teaching methods and materials becomes a hurdle for students in comprehending academic subjects and lesson content, leading to the identification of the inability to grasp these subjects and plans as a significant consequence of insufficient teaching methods and resources.

3.2. *Mechanisms for success in Integrating Gender and Development*—Considering the widespread gender-related challenges, educators are tasked with incorporating gender and development into their lessons. The complexity of factors that may impede the successful integration of gender and development could lead teachers to feel stressed and anxious. There-

fore, having effective coping strategies becomes essential. In times of stress or adversity, individuals often employ coping methods to navigate challenging emotions. These strategies play a crucial role in helping individuals handle difficult situations while preserving their mental well-being.

3.2.1. *Teacher Training and Professional Development*—Comprehensive teacher training provides educators the skills to identify and challenge biases and stereotypes in curriculum materials, classroom interactions, and teaching methods. This prepares teachers to actively contribute to positive change by promoting gender-sensitive language and content, creating inclu-

sive environments where every student feels valued. Moreover, ongoing professional development empowers teachers to establish classrooms that embrace diverse gender identities, ensuring respect and support for transgender and non-binary students. Inclusive classrooms serve as secure spaces for students to express their authentic selves, enhancing their learning experiences. Training programs focusing on Gender and Development (GAD) encourage teachers to guide students in critically analyzing media, literature, and historical narratives that perpetuate harmful gender stereotypes. This cultivates critical thinking skills, empowering students to question societal norms and advocate for equality. A gender-sensitive approach to teacher training incorporates considerations of gender disparity into all aspects of an educator's responsibilities. This method builds upon the foundational principles of student-centric education and empowering teaching techniques, adding a discerning perspective that scrutinizes the gender-related aspects of the learning environment. Furthermore, it examines how this setting reflects and responds to gender-based imbalances in the broader society (Hamdani, S. 2020, December). Adequate and relevant instruction plays a pivotal role in enhancing professional skills. With proper guidance on integrating Gender and Development in Education, educators gain the ability to craft personalized learning experiences, develop curriculum materials that enhance student achievement, and elevate their competence and innovative capabilities. An educator's level of familiarity and expertise significantly influences their students (iCEV, T., 2022).

3.2.2. Life Skills and Empowerment Education—In the drive for gender equality and societal progress, education emerges as a powerful force. However, genuine gender parity goes beyond mere access to education; it requires fostering essential life skills and empowerment education. These elements challenge conventional

norms, nurture self-confidence, and empower individuals of all genders to flourish. Integrating such components is crucial for effectively embedding Gender and Development (GAD) principles into educational systems. Addressing gender biases and misconceptions across the entire educational journey, spanning from early schooling to continuous learning, holds the potential to mitigate gender disparities in various domains of society. A case in point is the prevalent division of genders in the job market stemming from distinct educational and vocational preferences made during school and university years, encompassing students and educators alike. Additionally, instances of gender-related violence and discriminatory language occur within educational environments. Hence, it is imperative to dismantle and confront gender-centric stereotypes within the realms of education and training. (European Institute for Gender Equality, 2023) Young individuals must acquire fundamental life skills like analytical and innovative thinking, decision-making, and proficient communication to mature into capable adults. Equally important are abilities such as cultivating self-worth, fostering positive relationships, challenging detrimental gender stereotypes, and gaining access to healthcare. Although significant for youth globally, these proficiencies hold particular significance for adolescents who lack accurate insights and guidance to make impactful choices, such as entering intimate relationships, remaining in education, and addressing instances of mistreatment. Unfortunately, a considerable number of children are deprived of educational opportunities that encompass instruction in life skills. (Life Skills Education - World Education, 2022)

3.2.3. Textbook and Learning Material Evaluation—Integrating Gender and Development (GAD) principles into education is vital for achieving gender equality and addressing societal disparities. A critical aspect of this integration is the evaluation of textbooks and

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes on the Coping Mechanism of High School Teachers in Integrating Gender and Development learning materials used in educational settings.

Textbook and learning material evaluation is pivotal in ensuring that education promotes inclusivity, challenges gender stereotypes, and empowers learners of all genders. Evaluating textbooks enables educators to assess whether the content reflects diverse gender identities, backgrounds, and experiences. When learners see themselves and individuals of all genders represented positively and accurately, it enhances their sense of belonging and validates the experiences of various communities. Evaluating textbooks is crucial to make sure they match their intended goals and objectives. It helps gauge whether students can use what they have learned to bring about lasting changes in behavior and skills relevant to their specific situation. Evaluation also allows instructional designers to get everyone on the same page, ensuring that the instruction meets organizational objectives. (Calhoun, C., Sahay, S., Wilson, M. 2021) When it comes to Gender and Development in education, evaluating textbooks and learning materials becomes a key tool. By carefully examining and choosing materials that challenge biases, promote inclusivity, and empower learners of all genders, educators play a vital role in creating a learning space that reads individuals for a diverse and fair society.

3.3. *Insights learned from the experiences of the informants*—Throughout the interview process, numerous insights into educational concepts were obtained by exploring instructors’ challenges and experiences when integrating gender and development into classroom education.

3.3.1. *Complexity of Gender Integration*—The complexity of gender integration refers to the intricate and multifaceted nature of incorporating gender perspectives, equality, and development principles into various aspects of society, particularly in educational settings. This complexity arises from the intersection of cultural norms, historical biases, social dynamics, and systemic inequalities that shape individuals’ perceptions and behaviors related to gender. Entrenched Cultural Norms and Beliefs result in the pervasive presence of gender roles and stereotypes within societies. These ingrained norms influence how individuals anticipate and conduct themselves from a young age. Addressing and transforming these norms necessitates directly addressing longstanding traditions that have endured through generations. According to an article by Ashley Enriquez (2023), a clear example of how ingrained norms and beliefs about gender persist is evi-

dent in the Philippines. Despite being recognized as one of the most gender-equal countries globally, as indicated by the World Economic Forum's Global Gender Gap report, the Philippines still contends with a society dominated by patriarchal values. A report from the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS) in 2015 discovered that this patriarchal culture is deeply rooted within social frameworks, having been ingrained through historical colonization and religious teachings from the Church. In essence, gender integration's complexity arises from the need to address deeply rooted societal norms, challenge power dynamics, and navigate many factors that influence how gender is understood and experienced. Successful integration requires a comprehensive and nuanced approach that acknowledges these complexities and works toward holistic change.

3.3.2. Importance of Teacher Training— In an era of increasing global interconnectivity and diversity, providing teachers with training in gender and development enables them to ready students for interactions in the real world, where empathy, comprehension, and consideration for all genders are paramount. Proficient educators play a pivotal role in disrupting the cycle of gender inequality and nurturing attitudes of parity and empowerment in forthcoming generations. This can potentially effect enduring societal changes by progressively altering prevailing gender norms. Educated teachers evolve into affirmative role models, exemplifying respectful conduct, gender parity, and impartiality, thereby influencing the perspectives and conduct of students within and beyond the confines of the classroom. Teacher education or training is an ongoing and perpetual endeavor that enhances educators' instructional abilities, allows them to acquire fresh insights, and cultivates improved expertise. This, in turn, contributes to enhancing students' learning experiences. Research and various studies indicate that proficient classroom management by teach-

ers results in heightened student engagement and improved educational outcomes, in contrast to situations where classroom management skills are lacking. (Vinod Kakumanu, 2018) Teachers represent the most pivotal asset in enhancing the caliber of education. The competencies, knowledge, and practical insights teachers bring to their classrooms substantially influence students' learning proficiency and accomplishments. The impact of teachers is a determining factor in whether a student attains success or faces setbacks. By concentrating on teacher education and continuous enhancement, educational institutions can augment their aptitude to provide students with superior learning encounters. Programs for teacher training should be thoughtfully crafted to equip educators with the means to navigate present and future challenges effectively. (Ecole, 2023).

3.3.3. Long-Term Perspective on GAD— The integration of gender and development is a prolonged endeavor demanding enduring dedication. This underscores that advancement may not be instantaneous, but a steadfast endeavor can yield substantial transformation over time. A long-term perspective in GAD involves recognizing that achieving genuine gender equality is a complex and gradual process. It goes beyond short-term interventions and seeks to create enduring shifts in attitudes, norms, and structures. This perspective acknowledges that deeply entrenched gender biases and inequalities cannot be eradicated overnight but require persistent efforts and strategic planning. One of the key advantages of a long-term perspective is its ability to sustain momentum for change. GAD initiatives often encounter obstacles and setbacks, but a commitment to the long term enables stakeholders to persevere through challenges. Sustainable progress is achieved by consistently pushing against barriers and promoting inclusive practices over time. Cultural norms and societal structures that perpetuate gender inequalities are deeply ingrained. A long-term

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes on Educational Insights Learned from the experiences of the informants

perspective acknowledges the need for cultural and social transformation. This involves engaging in continuous dialogue, raising awareness, and challenging norms that reinforce discriminatory behaviors. Over time, these efforts can lead to shifts in attitudes and beliefs at both individual and community levels. A long-term approach in GAD recognizes the role of education in fostering change. Educational institutions are instrumental in shaping future generations' perceptions of gender roles and responsibilities. By incorporating gender-sensitive curricula and promoting respectful interactions, education becomes a vehicle for challenging stereotypes and promoting equality. Limited initiatives have been launched to ensure the continuity of a long-term outlook on Gender and Development. One such initiative involves establishing gender equality as the encompassing and persistent

developmental objective. In contrast, gender mainstreaming entails a collection of distinct, strategic strategies and both practical and organizational methods embraced to accomplish this objective. Gender mainstreaming aims to fuse gender equality within national public and private entities across overarching or localized policies, as well as within services and specialized programs. Ultimately, it seeks to overhaul prejudiced social institutions, legal frameworks, cultural conventions, and community practices that curtail women's rights to property or hinder their access to public spaces. (UN Women (2019) long-term perspective on Gender and Development is integral to achieving sustainable and meaningful progress in addressing gender inequalities. It requires persistent efforts to transform attitudes, institutions, and systems that perpetuate discrimination.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter provided a concise overview of the research, followed by conclusions from the study's discoveries. It also delved into future paths for educators with expertise in incorporating Gender and Development into their lessons. The discussion further explored the management of challenges and drew insights about education from the experiences shared by the informants.

4.1. Findings of the Study—Gender and Development (GAD) functions as a developmental strategy to level the playing field regard-

ing the positions, circumstances, and interactions of both women and men. This is achieved through its impact on the various stages of

policy formation, planning, allocation of resources, execution, and assessment. The purpose was to tackle gender-related matters and issues hindering women's comprehensive advancement. GAD primarily centers on two key frameworks, namely Gender Roles and Social Relations Analysis. Gender and Development is not just a concept; it was a pivotal force driving positive change in societies worldwide. Its importance lies in its potential to dismantle oppressive norms, promote equality, empower women and marginalized genders, and reshape policies for the better. GAD is a compass guiding us towards a future where everyone can realize their full potential, regardless of gender. As we navigate the complexities of the modern world, embracing the principles of Gender and Development becomes essential and imperative for building a just and prosperous society. This research was done to identify the experiences of High School teachers when integrating Gender and development inside the classroom.

4.2. *Implications*—The outcomes of my analysis unveiled notable findings as follows. Interviews were conducted with ten (10) teachers from various high schools in the Tugbok District, each with diverse backgrounds. The experiences of elementary school teachers in integrating Gender and Development (GAD) resulted in four themes: Lack of training, Deep-Rooted Gender Stereotypes, and Lack of Suitable Teaching Resources. Additionally, the teachers' strategies for dealing with the challenges of GAD integration were significant. This presentation highlighted three emerging themes: Teacher Training and Professional Development, Life Skills and Empowerment Education, and Textbook and Learning Material Evaluation. These findings are crucial for comprehending teachers' challenges when incorporating GAD in the classroom. Furthermore, policymakers, teachers, and anyone interested in enhancing students' educational experiences should consider our recommendations and find-

ings.

4.3. *Future Directions*—The comprehension of GAD principles among educators can be improved by workshops, seminars, and online courses, which would easily equip them to incorporate the concepts into their teaching methods. Additionally, the establishment of comprehensive training initiatives can be facilitated by a collaborative approach comprising educational institutions, government entities, and non-governmental groups. It was imperative to prioritize teacher training and continued professional growth. It should be a top priority to address the noted deficiency in training on integrating gender and development (GAD). In order to dismantle ingrained gender stereotypes, inclusive and varied curricula must be developed and implemented. Educational materials must be thoroughly examined to ensure they dispel misconceptions and encourage more gender-equitable depiction. Furthermore, promoting open communication and understanding in schools can help dispel preconceptions and create a more welcoming environment. Moreover, the recognized deficiency of appropriate pedagogical materials demands financial support for creating materials tailored to GAD. This could entail writing lesson plans, textbooks, and multimedia materials addressing gender views in various topic areas. Good, gender-sensitive educational resources can be produced by curriculum creators, educational publishers, and GAD specialists working together. In conclusion, this study sheds light on the experiences of high school teachers in integrating Gender and Development into their classrooms. The identified themes of lack of training, deep-rooted gender stereotypes, and insufficient teaching resources underline the need for targeted interventions and systemic changes. The coping mechanisms teachers employ, such as ongoing professional development, life skills education, and material evaluation, provide valuable insights into effective strategies for overcoming these challenges.

In the future, a concerted effort from policy-makers, educational institutions, and relevant stakeholders was necessary to create an environment that supports GAD integration. We can foster a more inclusive and gender-sensitive educational system by addressing these challenges head-on and implementing the recommended strategies. This, in turn, would contribute to shaping a generation of students with a nuanced understanding of gender issues and a commitment to promoting equality and diversity in all aspects of life. Finally, similar qualitative research across the nation may be used to gain a broader understanding and more insights from diverse participants in this study, deepening the information on teachers' experiences in integrating Gender and Development (GAD) into their instruction.

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